

General combining ability effects of parents for grain traits^a at TNRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1991-92 wet season.

Parent	Grain yield (g)	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel length-breadth ratio	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	Linear ^b elongation ratio	Breadthwise ^c expansion ratio	Elongation ^d index
<i>Line</i>									
TKM9	-5.61*	-0.04*	0.12*	-0.20*	-0.28*	0.18*	-0.09*	0.01	-0.06*
ADT37	-2.23*	-0.52*	0.22*	-0.54*	-0.80*	0.14*	0.01	-0.07*	0.06*
ADT39	4.69*	-0.05*	-0.05*	0.02	-0.15*	0.06*	0.001	0.08*	-0.05*
IR50	-2.62*	0.64*	-0.16*	0.58*	0.96*	-0.25*	0.02	-0.03	0.03*
Improved White Ponni	5.77*	-0.04*	-0.11*	0.14*	0.27*	-0.14*	0.06*	0.02	0.03*
SE	0.83	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01
<i>Tester</i>									
ADT41	4.39*	0.16*	-0.003	0.08*	0.05	0.10*	-0.03*	0.05*	-0.07*
Pusa Basmati 1	-2.51*	-0.13*	-0.04*	0.01	0.26*	-0.15*	0.06*	-0.04*	0.08*
Kasturi	-1.88*	-0.04*	0.04*	-0.09*	-0.31*	0.05*	-0.03*	-0.01	-0.01
SE	0.64	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01

^aSignificant at 5% level. ^bRatio of mean length of cooked rice to mean length of milled rice. ^cRatio of mean breadth of cooked rice to mean breadth of milled rice. ^dRatio of mean L B ratio of cooked rice to mean L-B ratio of milled rice.

Evaluation of rice diallel crosses in semidry condition by combining ability analysis

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Rice is grown on 2 million ha in Tamil Nadu, India. Only about 8% of this area is under limited irrigation, meaning that early drought is common. Drought warrants systematic research on developing rice varieties that withstand considerable moisture stress at early growth stages. We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of six parents: TKM9 (P1) and PMK1 (P3), improved drought-tolerant varieties; AS26556 (P2), recently released early drought-tolerant variety; Poongar (P6), a traditional unimproved low-yielding local drought-tolerant variety; and IR64 (P4) and ADT37 (P5), improved high-yielding varieties susceptible to drought. We also examined the specific combining ability (SCA) of 15 F₁s of direct crosses in a 6 × 6 diallel design under semidry conditions during 1992 wet season.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications in three locations: Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai; Agricultural Research Station,

GCA and SCA effects across locations for grain yield and other traits.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1992 wet season.

Parent/hybrid	Plant height	Heading date	Productive tillers	Root weight	Biomass	Grain yield
<i>GCA</i>						
P1	-6.28**	-0.40**	0.30**	-0.49**	0.77**	0.54**
P2	-1.76**	1.24**	-0.36**	-0.45**	-2.01**	0.49**
P3	9.08**	5.28**	0.01	1.39**	2.77**	-0.41**
P4	-5.73**	1.45**	0.74**	-1.13**	-1.33**	-0.07
P5	-0.40**	-7.35**	-0.81**	-0.34**	0.25	-0.71**
P6	4.72**	-7.35**	-0.81**	1.01**	1.09**	-0.71**
<i>SCA</i>						
P1/P2	1.99**	-0.03	0.41*	-0.56*	0.94	0.76*
P1/P3	1.00**	-0.68**	-0.93**	0.87*	1.68**	1.04**
P1/P4	-3.16**	-0.79**	2.71**	0.18	-0.37	-2.02**
P1/P5	2.33**	0.71**	-0.99**	0.42*	1.25*	0.39
P1/P6	2.78**	-0.55**	0.64**	-1.14**	0.67	0.14
P2/P3	3.36**	-2.60**	1.95**	0.07	4.33**	4.74**
P2/P4	6.98**	-0.66**	-1.62**	0.73**	2.00**	-0.30
P2/P5	0.37	3.02**	1.92**	-1.01**	-1.49**	-0.08
P2/P6	0.91**	1.25**	-3.14**	-1.01**	-1.49**	-0.08
P3/P4	2.82**	1.26**	1.32**	1.07**	2.91**	1.44**
P3/P5	2.84**	2.87**	-1.29**	-0.65**	0.18	0.50
P3/P6	-1.87**	-2.35**	-1.81**	-0.06	0.01	0.60**
P4/P5	-0.20	0.56**	-0.08	0.07	-3.17**	-2.86**
P4/P6	1.29**	-1.94**	0.19	-1.82**	0.46	1.33**
P5/P6	-0.53**	-0.01	-0.42	0.33	-0.68	-0.08
<i>GCA</i>						
SE	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.22	0.13
CD (5%)	0.25	0.17	0.22	0.25	0.61	0.36
CD (1%)	0.33	0.22	0.29	0.33	0.80	0.43
<i>SCA</i>						
SE	0.21	0.13	0.19	0.21	0.51	0.31
CD (5%)	0.58	0.36	0.53	0.58	1.41	0.86
CD (1%)	0.76	0.47	0.69	0.77	1.86	1.13

** , * = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

Paramakudi, and Cotton Research Station, Srivilliputtur, Tamil Nadu, India. The crop was directly sown and maintained under rainfed condition up to 45 d after sowing, at which time the crop was irrigated. Plots were 3-m rows with 15 plants each at 30- × 20-cm row and plant spacing. Among the many physiological indices available, the most reliable, such as root weight and biomass productivity, were used to measure drought. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for observation and analysis.

Among the six parents tested, PMK1 (P3) was the superior general combiner for special drought characters (root weight, biomass productivity, plant height, and earliness). TKM9 (P1) for grain yield and IR64 (P4) for productive tillers were good general combiners. PMK1 (P3), a good combiner for all traits except grain yield and productive tillers, and IR64, a poor combiner for many characters, were crossed and showed positive significant SCA effects for all traits studied (see table). This shows that superior hybrids may also be obtained

from high/low GCA parental combinations. After PMK1/IR64, hybrids AS26556 (good combiner)/PMK1 (good combiner) and TKM9 (medium combiner)/PMK1 (good combiner) were next in superiority.

The differential combining ability of PMK1 with other parental types reveals that using this genotype as a potential parent in breeding programs to develop semidry-tolerant types may produce useful transgressive segregants in the segregating generation. ■

Combining ability of some varieties for grain quality traits in diallel mating system

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We evaluated six popular high-yielding rice genotypes (IR50, TKM9, ADT37, ADT39, ADT40, and Improved White

Ponni) and their 15 F₁ hybrids obtained through diallel mating (without reciprocals) for combining ability of 10 grain quality traits.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design during 1993 dry season and replicated three times. Hills were spaced at 20 × 10 cm, with a single seedling per hill. Five plants per replication were evaluated following standard procedures for 10 grain quality traits:

kernel length, kernel breadth, kernel thickness, L-B ratio, kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, linear elongation ratio, breadthwise expansion ratio, hulling, and milling.

The variances due to general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) were significant except for kernel length. This indicated that the genotypes differed widely for the traits studied. Higher GCA variance than SCA

Table 1. Analysis of variance for combining ability.

Source of variation	df	Mean squares									
		Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel thickness (mm)	L:B	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	Linear elongation ratio	Breadthwise expansion ratio	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)
General combining ability (GCA)	5	0.205***	0.205**	0.046**	0.378**	0.368**	0.094**	0.011**	0.018**	3.874**	4.037**
Specific combining ability (SCA)	15	0.005	0.005**	0.016**	0.160**	0.374**	0.042**	0.011**	0.015**	2.601**	2.648**
Error	40	0.016	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.011

*** = significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Estimates of general combining ability effects of parents for different grain quality traits.

Parent	Trait									
	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Kernel thickness (mm)	L:B	Kernel length after cooking (mm)	Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	Linear elongation ratio	Breadthwise expansion ratio	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)
IR50	0.09**	-0.22**	-0.01**	0.29**	0.40**	-0.03**	0.01**	0.06**	-0.43**	-0.33**
ADT37	-0.18**	0.15**	0.02**	-0.32**	-0.14**	0.21**	0.06**	-0.02**	0.37**	0.70**
TKM9	0.01	0.16**	0.05**	-0.04**	0.05**	-0.04**	-0.01	-0.07**	0.03**	-0.34**
ADT39	0.02	-0.05**	-0.07**	0.15**	-0.07**	0.01	0.01	0.02**	1.19**	1.08**
ADT40	0.06	0.10**	0.10**	-0.15**	-0.02	-0.04**	-0.05**	-0.02**	-0.52**	-0.49**
Improved White Ponni	0.01	-0.14**	-0.10**	0.07**	-0.21**	-0.11**	-0.02**	0.03**	-0.64**	-0.63**
SE (g)	0.041	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.014	0.010	0.004	0.004	0.035	0.034

** = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively.